

Research Article

Biodegradable Straw

Wan Noor Aida Wan Muhamad^{1,*}, Lim Shaio Ai², Siti Rosmanirah Che Rashid³, and Aiman Farid Mohd Radzi⁴¹ aida@pjk.edu.my² limshaioai@gmail.com³ a26rosma@gmail.com⁴ aimanrdzi29@gmail.com

* Correspondence: aida@pjk.edu.my; 014-5008054

Abstract: Biodegradable straws are developed to address the rising demand in Malaysia's food and beverage sector, providing an alternative to market straws made from low water-resistant starches like rice and cassava straw. This project aims to formulate biodegradable straw made from corn leaf waste and to identify the durability and biodegradability of formulated biodegradable straw produced from corn leaves waste. The production process involves five steps which is collecting *Zea mays* corn leaves, extracting fibres by cooking with bicarbonate soda, preparing pulp with carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), moulding the straws, and coating them with palm oil wax which is a safe-to-eat compound. The durability and biodegradability test of various straw formulations. T1 is broken rice and tapioca starch straw, as well as three different formulations of biodegradable straw that are made from corn leaf fibre plus different percentage of Carboxymethyl Cellulose (CMC), T2 is 5% CMC, T3 is 15% CMC, and T4 is 25% CMC. The test is done with 3 replicates; every replicate takes 5 samples for each Treatment. The test found the best formulated straw is T4 straw with 25% CMC. The durability rate is 05:34 minutes ($p < .000$) and the significant rate of biodegradability rate is 5.69% ($p < .001$). The high durability of T4 straw due to carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) presents a cross-linking structure with corn leaf fibre to perform hydrophobic structure reduce the water penetration when soaking in water. The high biodegradability in T4 straw is due to corn leaf fibre is naturally rich in cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. Lastly, the biodegradable straw offers an environmentally friendly product, promotes good farm waste management practices, ensures safety in usage, introduces green culture to society, and helps farmers in generating high profits.

Keywords: Biodegradable Straw; Corn Leaves; Carboxymethyl Cellulose.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Drinking straw is a tool that makes drinking easier by delivering the liquid into mouth through a tube. The mouth's suction reduces the air pressure within, forcing liquid through straws and into mouths because of atmospheric pressure. According to a study, Malaysia generated 0.94 million tons of improperly disposed of plastic waste, of which 0.14 to 0.37 million tons might have ended up in the ocean (Ministry of Energy, Science, Technology, environment & Climate, Malaysia., 2018). In addition, the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) is a strategy or approach to waste management that minimizes waste at the product level by creating environmentally friendly items (Kamaruddin, 2021). The manufacturer discovered some alternative material to replace the use of conventional fossil-based plastics. For instance, alternative straws made of biodegradable materials like paper, bamboo and starch or reusable materials like silicon, glass, and metals (Kamaruddin, 2021).

Biodegradable straw is an alternative to Polystyrene (PS) or Polypropylene (PP) plastic drinking straws. The paper straws known as biodegradable straws that are produced from hardwood fibres and they have the advantages of being fully biodegradable and inexpensive. Biobased polylactic acid (PLA) straws are manufactured from corn, beet sugar, and sugarcane monomers through condensation polymerization of lactic acid monomers or ring-opening polymerization of lactides (Moy et al., 2021). Straws that included polylactic acid (PLA) require continuous temperatures above 60 degrees Celsius by industrial composting. Other than that, the starch straw is produced using starches from wheat, rice, corn, cassava and potatoes as the main raw materials. The starch-based straws sensitive to moisture, straw easily become soggy, swollen, and collapse in water due to hydroxyl groups in starch causing its hydrophilic nature. The starch film have higher water vapour permeability and lower tensile strength under higher moisture conditions. (Jiang et al., 2020).

Plastic based straws play a crucial role to society as an effective tool that commonly found in restaurants and beverage shop. However, the unrestrained use of plastic straws has produced in large amounts of plastic rubbish, endangering human health and environment. In recent years, various types of biodegradable straws have been promoted, raising consumers' awareness of reducing the use of plastic straws. However, most of the biodegradable that found in the market is low durability in liquid, expensive market price, deforestation, difficulty in degrading and the list goes on. Thus, the aims of the project are to formulate biodegradable straw made from corn leaves waste, identify the durability of formulated biodegradable straw produced from corn leaves waste. And lastly to identify the biodegradability of formulated biodegradable straw produced from corn leaves waste.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Research Method

The project aims to formulate Biodegradable Straw that made of corn leaf, this research finds the compostable and suitable material for making the sturdy drinking straw. In this study, the leaves of sweet corn (*Zea mays*) are collected at the sweet corn field in Politeknik Jeli Kelantan. The main steps in the biodegradable straw production includes corn leaf preparation, corn fibre extraction, pulp preparation, straw moulding, and straw coating. The data analysis will be focusing on the durability of biodegradable straw and biodegradability of biodegradable straw made. The leaf's fibres from sweet corn (*Zea mays*) will be extracted by using baking soda then leaf's fibres from corn are produced and mixed CMC (Carboxymethyl Cellulose) powder as stabiliser to produce pulp for straw moulding. This project produces the high hydro stability straw owing to the oil palm wax used in the straw coating.

2.2 Product Design

Big size straw was design which is the 6mm diameter straw and 12mm diameter straw. The large size of Biodegradable Straws is designed with suitable measurement to achieve the demand of drinking straws needed in the boba tea market.

2.3 Procedure

2.3.1 Corn Leaf Preparation

Figure 1. Corn Leaf Preparation (Alcachupas et al., 2020) with modification

2.3.2 Corn Leaf Fibre Extraction

Figure 2. Corn Leaf Fibre Extraction (Guru and Kumar, 2021) with modification

2.3.3 Pulp Preparation

Figure 3. Pulp Preparation (Guru and Kumar, 2021) with modification

2.3.4 Straw Moulding

Figure 4. Straw Moulding (Alvarado et al., 2021) with modification

2.3.5 Straw Coating

Figure 5. Straw Coating (Ghazali et al., 2021) with modification

2.4 Testing methods

2.4.1 Durability Test

The durability of straw is tested, this research focus on the time taken by different formulated straw such as corn leaves biodegradable straw and broken rice, and tapioca starch straw become swelling or collapse in tap water. The durability of straw related to the ability of water absorb by the straw, their water uptake tests to detect the presence of polymers bonds that can induced by the percentage of weight gain in polymer following of straw swelling (Putra & Saputra., 2020).

Table 1. Treatment of Biodegradable Straw

T1	Control Group (broken rice and tapioca starch straw)
T2	5 % CMC powder
T3	15 % CMC powder
T4	25 % CMC powder

Figure 6. Biodegradable Straw Durability Test (Alcachupas et al., 2020) with modification

2.4.2 Biodegradability Test

The soil burial test of biodegradability for straw is tested, this research focus on the time taken by different formulated straw such as corn leaves biodegradable straw and broken rice and tapioca starch straw to degrade in soil at greenhouse with aerobic conditions for 10 days. The biodegradability of straw is affected by the material in straw due to the building blocks in polyester. The rate of biodegrade for straw is faster under humid soil conditions and high temperatures soil conditions. (Wang et al., 2024).

The weight loss of straw during biodegradability calculated by this formula.

$$WL (\%) = \text{Percentage of weight loss}$$

$$W_o = \text{Initial weight}$$

$$W_f = \text{Final weight}$$

$$WL = \frac{W_o - W_f}{W_o} \times 100\%.$$

Figure 7. Soil Burial Test of Biodegradability Test (Nissa et al., 2019) with modification

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Durability Test

Figure 8. Mean Measurement of Biodegradable Straw Durability Test

Figure 8 shows the mean of biodegradable straw durability test. Significant rate of ($p < .000$). T4 straw closely behind the T1 straw which is 13 seconds. The mean durability of T1 straw is highest among the treatment which is 5.47 minutes. Next, the mean durability of T2 straw is lowest among the treatment which is 02.05 minutes. Moreover, the mean durability of T4 straw is high than T3 straw which is 05:34 minutes compared to 03:00 minutes. T1 and T4 showed greater durability, they might be more suitable for market demand which is last longer for drinking. Conversely, T3 and T2 demonstrated shorter durability, suggesting that they should be further developed or that their use should be taken into consideration in some applications where shorter usage times are acceptable.

Figure 9. Mean Measurement of Biodegradable Straw Percentage of Weight Loss (%) by Treatment

Figure 9 highlight the simple line mean of percentage of weight loss % by treatment. Significant rate of ($df=59, p < .001$). The T1 shows lowest mean of percentage of weight loss among treatments, -73.74%. This data indicates the T1 straw have lowest biodegradability rate. Secondly, the T2 straw have highest mean of percentage of weight loss among the treatments which is 62.61%. Therefore, the T2 have highest biodegradability rate. Thirdly, the mean of percentage of weight loss for T3 is higher than T4 which is 40.44% compared to 5.69%. This shows that the T3 straw have higher biodegradability rate compared to T4 straw.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Durability Test

4.1.1 High Durability of T1 Straw

The broken rice and tapioca starch straw (T1) which made from broken rice and tapioca as starch component which provided the straw with better hydro stability in water. The factors result in longer durability of broken rice and tapioca starch straw (T1) in tap water are strong hydrogen bonds in straws, retrogradation of starch straw, high amylopectin content, present glucose monomer as linkage molecule, present of starch cohesive agent and extrusion and moulding techniques of straw of biodegradable straw.

Firstly, the creation of strong hydrogen bonds during the retrogradation of starch are importance to produce rigid broken rice and tapioca starch straw (T1). Next, the process done between the double helix structure of starch molecule (Cui et al., 2023). Previous research found that the retrograded starch straws have the excellent mechanical performance which is high flexural strength of ≈ 14000 g (Cui et al., 2023). Additionally, after soaking starch in 25 °C water for one hour, the straw shows hydro stability is 22.9 times stronger than the wet mechanical strength of starch straw (Cui et al., 2023).

Meanwhile, the corn leaf fibre and 25% carboxymethyl cellulose straw (T4) have high durability in water due to several reasons. For instance, form by hydrophobicity component, higher

carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) composition, cross-linking structure in molecule and fibre reinforcement of corn leaves of biodegradable straw.

Firstly, the corn leaf fibre and 25% carboxymethyl cellulose straw (T4) perform high durability in water due the higher carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) composition and corn leaf fibre. It is the hydrophobicity of component and fibre reinforcement in straw. The forming a cross-linked network with the corn leaf fibres, carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) integration improves the straw's resistance to water penetration and significantly decreases water absorption. In addition to giving the straw its hydrophobic properties, this cross-linking strengthens its structure and keeps it from collapsing in a solution liquid (Liu et al., 2021). Research proves that the using of 15% carboxymethyl cellulose in film improved the mechanical properties with tensile strength of 44.8 MPa (Liu et al., 2021).

Additionally, the high carboxymethyl cellulose concentration in corn leaf fibre and 25% carboxymethyl cellulose straw (T4) produce the more rigid and water resistance straw. CMC enhances the molecular network inside the straw by acting as a binder and structural enhancer agent. The previous research shows that, the high carboxymethyl cellulose, the lower mass grow of fibre film of soak in water. Results shows that mass grow of 10% carboxymethyl cellulose is 1750% and 25% carboxymethyl cellulose is 1650% (Boruvkova et al., 2011). Next, another previous research tests the swelling of coconut fibers carboxymethyl cellulose in 25 °C distilled water for one hour. The result proven that the swelling capacity for 25% of CMC is 11.2 g/g, while 15% CMC is 10.4 g/g and 5% CMC is 8.6 g/g (Gichuki et al., 2023). The research shows that the carboxymethyl cellulose create hydrophobic barrier to resist water absorption. As the results corn leaf fibre and 25% carboxymethyl cellulose straw (T4) resistant to swelling in water compared to lower CMC treatment straw.

4.2 Biodegradability Test

4.2.1 Low Biodegradability Rate of T1 Straw

The low biodegradability rate in broken rice and tapioca starch straw (T1) owing to few reasons. For example, high starch content, hydrophilic properties of starch, high molecule weight, and high crystalline structure of biodegradable straw. The broken rice and tapioca starch straw (T1) low biodegradability rate due to the high starch content. This line with the statement of previous research (Putri & Falah., 2021), it found that the biodegradable straws which contain rich amount of unused rice flour than rice bran flour take longer time to decompose fully.

Next, the previous research found that the hydrophilic properties starch cause high absorbed water molecules to cause microorganisms in the environment to enter the biodegradable straw matrix, so that biodegradable straws are easily decomposed (Putri & Farah., 2021). The previous research result shows that the water uptake is 100% for straw samples from combinations of unused rice flour and rice bran flour, after 30 minutes of soaking in testing media in the form of aquadest (Putri & Farah., 2021). The high-water uptake value of the samples is likely due to the increased starch content resulting from the combination of rice flour and rice bran.

4.2.2 High Biodegradability Rate of T2, T3 and T4 Straw

Firstly, several reasons contribute to high biodegradability rate on the corn leaf fibre and 5% carboxymethyl cellulose straw (T2), the corn leaf fibre and 10% carboxymethyl cellulose straw (T3) and the corn leaf fibre and 25% carboxymethyl cellulose straw (T4). For examples, high corn leaf fibre of straw, lower crystallinity of straw molecule, and high fragmentation of straw.

The straw is made from high corn leaf fibre is naturally rich in cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. Cellulose and hemicellulose are polysaccharides that are more readily broken down by microbial enzymes. It is because the cellulose chains more accessible to microbial enzymes. This enhances the degradation process by making it easier for microorganisms to degrade the fibres. This line with the statement of previous research, the presence of cellulose enhances the straw's

biodegradability as microorganisms are more adept at degrading these polysaccharides (Shaghaleh et al., 2018).

Based on the previous research found that the leaf types of plant have fibre compound that easily biodegrade in soil (Brunšek et al., 2023). The fibre mass loss test done on hemp, jute, sisal, viscose, and Polylactic acid (PLA) fibres with 11 days in burial soil. The results shows that the percentage mass loss for hems is higher which is 44.51%, jute is 24.84, sisal is 7.92, viscose is 11.64, and polylactic acid (PLA) is 3.99% (Brunšek et al., 2023). This statement proves that lignocellulose fibres in plants have moisture absorption ability reduce biodegradation period. The fungi first attack the protective outer layer of leaf, bacteria penetrating into leaf's fibre as well as degrading the maximum cellulose, following with the decrease of tenacity (Brunšek et al., 2023).

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the production of biodegradable straw involves five main steps which are corn leaf preparation, corn leaf fibre extraction, pulp preparation, straw moulding, and straw coating. The biodegradable straw that made from corn leaves waste is easy to decompose in soil, apply good waste utilization in field, safe to use, introduce green culture to Malaysian and helps people to generate high profit. Next, the oil palm coating and Carboxymethyl Cellulose powder in pulp stabilizer ensure the final product is high durability when soaking water. The durability and biodegradability test of various straw formulations. T1 is broken rice and tapioca starch straw, as well as three different formulations of biodegradable straw that made from corn leaf fibre plus different percentage of Carboxymethyl Cellulose (CMC), T2 is 5% CMC, T3 is 15% CMC, and T4 is 25% CMC. The test done 3 replicates; every replicate takes 5 samples for each Treatment. The test found the best formulated straw is T4 straw with 25% CMC. The durability rate is 05:34 minutes ($p < .000$) and the significant rate of biodegradability rate is 5.69% ($p < .001$). The high durability of T4 straw due to arboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) present a cross-linking structure with corn leaf fibre to performance hydrophobic structure reduce the water penetration when soaking in water. Next, the high biodegradability in T4 straw is due to corn leaf fibre is naturally rich in cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin.

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